

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES FOR SELF-STUDY OF STUDENTS IN A CREDIT-MODULAR SYSTEM AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article reveals the credit-modular system of education in higher educational institutions, highlights the educational direction of historical education of students based on various approaches to the structure of the process of independent learning in the teaching of historical sciences, and the development of competencies for independent learning is revealed as a problem of the pedagogical process.*

Keywords: *competence, credit module, cognitive, didactic, component, category, anatomy, motive.*

In the system of credit and module in the world educational institutions, the training of personnel for the quality world labor market, the development of competencies for independent education of students increase the level of training, models and methods for the development of competencies for independent education of students in the Balonian educational system are being applied to the educational process. In such developed countries as the United States, Great Britain, England, Germany, France, China, Japan, South Korea, Russia, there is a competitive credit-modular system, a free operation of specialists in their professional field for the sectors of the economy of society, the development of training in professional and pedagogical training through professional and communicative competencies, systematic work is carried out to improve the

Higher education institutions where the credit modular education system is introduced History Education Educational direction in the teaching of historical sciences, several approaches can be observed in understanding the essence of students ' Independent Education: some authors give preference to the activity side of this issue, others - to psychological aspects. I.Ya.Lerner views independent education as the desire and ability to acquire knowledge formed in the process of purposeful creative search in students. The form of manifestation of independent education, according to didactics, is the solution by students of a cognitive task that represents a problem, The Independent solution of which leads to new knowledge and methods of solving it.

Cognitive tasks are not only a form of manifestation of independent learning, but also "... it also serves as a pedagogical tool for its formation" [70. – B.35].

Thus, the researcher follows an activity-based approach rather than based on his personal approaches.

N.A.Polovnikova [107] and L.P.Aristova [3] by taking into account the personal qualities of students and giving preference to a psychological and didactic approach to solving the existing problem, the educational direction of history education in the credit modular education system takes a different approach to the issue of developing independent education of students in the teaching of historical sciences. The work carried out by them is devoted to research on the prosessual aspect of the cognitive (cognitive) activity of students. Independent education refers to

N.A.Polovnikova understands such qualities of an individual as readiness (ability and aspiration) to carry out activities in an independent way, gaining purposeful knowledge.

The desire for cognitive activity, that is, the student's desire to acquire new knowledge, is determined by the presence of internal motives as well as the corresponding motives that make up the stimulating side of Independent Education. Ability is based on existing knowledge and the assimilation of methods of activity. Auxiliary knowledge knowledge is the content of independent education, while the methods of activity that serve to gain knowledge are its technical or prosessual aspect [107. – B.45].

T.I.Shamova considers the education of positive qualities for the reading and learning of an individual to be one of the main integrative qualities associated with the formation of a system of knowledge and methods of activity and their application and assimilation of new ones, as well as voluntary actions. This property in a person is characterized without any external factors as the desire and ability to acquire new knowledge and acquire methods of activity, to solve problems associated with the acquisition of knowledge [166]. – B. 9].

Independent education is formed and developed as a feature in a person's personality under the influence of external and internal factors that influence each other and dictate each other.

Internal factors consist in the personal characteristics of the student (innate abilities and inclinations, willpower, temperament, etc.) and life activities, the process of gaining knowledge is improved, acquired knowledge and methods of receiving this knowledge.

External factors are the whole society surrounding the students of the University of the pedagogical higher educational institution, the social environment in which he lives and the influence of the educational process.

Independent Education consists in the appearance, which is considered a system of internal formations and practical actions for self-education.

Independent education is such a feature in a person that it is a set of actions, abilities and knowledge that serve students, firstly, to carry out the activity of gaining knowledge and, secondly, to independently acquire general and special knowledge, skills and qualifications to solve personal important problems as a member of society.

The implied character of an individual is due to his self-development, which ultimately pursues the goal of namyon the student's own personality in society. The social side of the phenomenon is manifested in its stimulation and perception for the development of its knowledge and skills.

The level of knowledge formed before a certain period is a meaningful aspect of Independent Education; the complex of skills for independent acquisition of knowledge expresses its working composition; aspirations are manifested through the desire to read and learn (to improve one's mental, physical or moral qualities) and are aimed at achieving some socially conditioned goal; abilities, on the other hand, determine natural inclinations.

In the credit modular education system of higher education institutions, it is generally accepted that the educational direction of history education for students is made up of three main parts: motviation (stimulating), meaningful-practical and volitional.

The manifestation of the activity of gaining independent knowledge is, of course, connected by its motivations that determine the activity in which the goal is directed. The meaningful-practical component, on the other hand, involves having a system of prioritized knowledge and methods of mastering, which are mastered on the student side.

A steady desire to acquire new knowledge and encourage the assimilation of new methods of activity will come true only if the student has a certain system of priority knowledge and is able to master it independently.

Under the framework of the credit education system of higher educational institutions, the stimulating and meaningful-practical component of Independent Education of students in the study of historical subjects is closely related to volitional processes. In order to achieve the goal, students are required to act in a certain volitional manner in addition to desire. The concept of Independent Education is seamlessly connected with activities that serve to gain knowledge in an independent way as well as to gain independent knowledge. The development of one's own knowledge and skills in higher education institutions operating on the basis of a credit modular education system, the educational direction of history education to students is considered as a form of independent knowledge acquisition, which occurs through independent education in the teaching of historical sciences, through an activity that serves to acquire knowledge in a personal

Independent education is manifested through activities that serve to gain knowledge in an independent way, and in the process of engaging in the same kind of activity, it finds prosperity.

The activities of students to acquire independent knowledge are greatly influenced by various types of incentives.

If the incentive to teach and educate is the need for cognitive activity aimed at Reading and learning in students or mastering new knowledge and skills, such incentives are manifested in the form of various processes, objects, phenomena, knowledge, skills and skills [102]. – B.287].

Independent Education Promotion of activities can be conditionally divided into socio-psychological and pedagogical types: for example, all types of assessment of personal tasks for socio-psychological stimulation (approval, recognition, assessment, etc.) it is desirable to enter. The influence of the surrounding social environment (spiritual and material), which occupies a special place in the social life of students, is also important.

Pedagogical stimulation of the activity of acquiring knowledge in an independent way consists in the organization of the educational and educational process, which involves the solution of the following pedagogical tasks. For example, the formation and development of incentives aimed at acquiring new knowledge in an independent way, the development of self-education skills in a voluntary way, the formation and improvement of independent educational activities, including the formation of a positive emotional experience of acquiring new knowledge and skills in an independent way. The series of incentives mentioned above affect each other and complement each other. For example, spiritual stimulation helps an individual to realize himself and improve his social status. The social environment, in turn, actively affects the personal characteristics of students.

Pedagogical stimulation requires taking into account both the psychological characteristics of the student and the interpersonal relationships in the team. In institutions of Higher Education operating on the basis of the credit system, the direction of education of the student's history education is in close dialectical connection the prerequisites and resources and motives and incentives for independent education in the teaching of historical sciences. This system of incentives, which contributes to an increase in the level of development of the initial components of such personality traits, can affect students at a certain level of development of their knowledge and skills. In addition, self-education activities can also become a person's need for independent knowledge, that is, a source of independent educational activities.

Important conditions for such rotation are: duration of stimulation, its consistency and intensity.

Thus, the Independent Education of students is largely associated with psychological support, the formation (consciousness) of the needs for mastering social and new knowledge and skills, practical preparation of students for the implementation of independent educational activities, the level of influence of the social environment and the corresponding level of knowledge.

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